

THE ROLE OF ECONOMIC CONSCIOUSNESS AND ECONOMIC THINKING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMIC IMAGE OF THE WORLD.

Asrakulova Adiba Nabievna

Doctor of philosophy (PhD) philosophical sciences,
Teacher of Namangan state pedagogical institute
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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the role of economic consciousness and economic thinking in the development of the world economy, the leading factors of the development of the country's economy.

Keywords: society, economy, thinking, economic consciousness, economic thinking, development, country, people, market, education, knowledge.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о роли экономического сознания и экономического мышления в развитии мировой экономики, ведущих факторах развития экономики страны.

Ключевые слова: общество, экономика, мышление, экономическое сознание, экономическое мышление, развитие, страна, человек, рынок, образование, знание.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada iqtisodiy ong va iqtisodiy tafakkurning dunyo iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishdagi o'r iqtisodiyotini yuksaltirish uchun mamlakat quroli haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jamiyat, iqtisod, tafakkur, iqtisodiy ong, iqtisodiy tafakkur, jamiyat, mamlakat, xalq, bozor, tarbiya, bilim.

In the course of research, it will be effective to implement measures aimed at realizing the unlimited possibilities of economic consciousness and economic thinking, raising them to the level of modern requirements and turning them into the leading factor of increasing the economic power of the country in two directions.

The first is to expand the scope of the economic consciousness of the members of the society, to arm it with new modern knowledge in the field of economy, to form a perfect economic consciousness capable of fully reflecting the socio-economic existence among the broad strata of the population, to educate the masses of the people, all strata of the population.[1] Educating in the spirit of their requirements, enriching their minds with new, modern economic knowledge specific to the market economy. We think that these events should cover all sections of the population.

Improving the economic literacy of the country's population is a comprehensive event that requires the involvement of a large amount of financial

resources. In this respect, this event is very valuable to society. In the context of a shortage of financial resources, the question arises whether it is reasonable from the point of view of economic efficiency to spend a large amount of financial resources on arming the economic consciousness with new modern knowledge by increasing the economic literacy of all layers of the population? Of course, reasonable. Because the financial resources spent on arming the economic consciousness of the population with new modern knowledge have a multiplying effect on increasing the economic potential of the country and, as a result, become a reliable factor in the development of the country's economy.

As a result of the low level of consumer culture, in the country, in the use of rare and priceless economic resources, in the consumption of ready-made products and services made from them, great wastage is allowed, and the principles of thrift are grossly violated. [2] Especially in the processes of harvesting, transporting, storing and delivering the agricultural products created by the hard work of farmers, the economic literacy is not at the level of the requirements of the time, and a large part of the delicacies produced is due to the lack of economic intuition. is dying. Social production aims to improve the well-being of the country's population, to ensure the abundance of material and spiritual blessings, it is defined as the main goal, and it creates gross goods and services. If we take into account this golden rule of economic development, the faster we eliminate such losses caused by our lack of economic literacy and ignorance, the faster our life will be prosperous. The main goal of social production is not just the production of goodies, but ultimately their consumption and prosperity.

The second is to develop the ability to think economically in the country, especially among our youth, to form cognitive thinking skills in the population, and most importantly, to develop effective mechanisms to turn it into a leading factor of socio-economic development.

We believe that it is necessary to pay serious attention to improving the cognitive economic thinking of officials who have the opportunity to directly participate in the formation of the economic foundation of the country by accelerating the rate of economic growth and improving its quality. Employees of state bodies, leaders, businessmen, professors, researchers, economists, media workers can be included in this category. The thinking, economic thinking ability of persons belonging to this category is of decisive importance in ensuring the social and economic development of the country.[3] They collect, process, generalize, analyze data reflecting economic reality, determine the influence of

various factors, draw theoretical and practical conclusions based on them, promote the results of economic development among the people, and determine the directions of economic development in the future. directly participates in defining and making relevant decisions on their implementation.

In other words, the strata of the population belonging to this category, on the one hand, are responsible for the state of the national economy, its position in the globalized world economy, the rates and quality of economic growth. On the other hand, when the situation requires, they have the opportunity to directly influence the rate of socio-economic growth of the country, more precisely, to accelerate it. Therefore, it is necessary to increase their material and moral responsibility for mistakes and shortcomings made at the macro and micro level, and at the same time to create effective mechanisms of material and moral stimulation of their services in reaching high levels of development.[4] As the economic landscape of the world changes, the concepts of materiality, lifestyle, and well-being of the young generation are formed accordingly. For example, a few decades ago, the dreams and needs of our parents were significantly different from those of today's generation. In fact, along with the progress of development, it is natural for human needs to increase and material interests to grow. Accordingly, the development of the country's economy is becoming a necessary requirement.

Therefore, at the current stage of the socio-economic development of the countries of the world, integration and globalization are becoming increasingly stronger. In this case, the competitiveness of the economy of each country is determined, first of all, by the level of economic socialization, economic upbringing and economic orientation of the population living in the region. The state's policy on economic education, its reforms, the final indicator of all scientific, socio-economic developments, in short, economic literacy is characterized by the provision of competitiveness. Therefore, creating conditions for young people to participate independently in economic relations, encouraging their achievements in this process and directing them to correct their shortcomings in time is the main key of any development. In the action strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, in the concepts of national economy development of the Development Strategy for 2022-2026, and other draft laws, opportunities were created to encourage the implementation of this rule. Today, as we are concerned about the economic progress of our country and its further development, we should teach

not only the adults, but also our youth, who are the successors of the third renaissance, to master the economic teachings of the above thinkers.[5]

It is about people of today having economic knowledge and understanding, being able to make free decisions in this regard, having the right approach to the process, and creating conditions for this. This can be clearly seen in the example of Uzbekistan's reforms in recent years, active efforts to liberalize the social and political life of the country. In short, first of all, the views on social life and changes in consciousness in Eastern philosophy serve as an important spiritual heritage, value in deepening the understanding that the implementation of social changes in our lives today is related to economic consciousness. [6] In every speech and works of the head of our state, the problems of the owner class, entrepreneurs, small business, peasants and farms are given a special place, which proves how important it is to strengthen the socio-economic education of the citizens of New Uzbekistan, to form economic thinking, and the role of components of economic consciousness in the personality structure. After all, preventing the socio-economic decline that may occur during the transition to market relations, filling the place of possible economic backwardness with healthy ideas, scientifically based knowledge, concepts and worldview is an important task in the formation of the personality of a business person.

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